

European Research Council
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European Research Council (ERC)

ERC Data Management Plan

Template

ERC OPEN RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

European Research Council
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Project Acronym	Project Number
IN-ROME	101054143

Template for the ERC Open Research Data Management Plan (DMP). The following sections should describe how you plan to make the project data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). Each of the following five issues should be addressed with a level of detail appropriate to the project.

SUMMARY (*dataset¹ reference and name; origin and expected size of the data generated/collected; data types and formats*)

The project will create the following datasets:

1. GIS system comprising of vectorized maps of the Catasto Gregoriano Profano and other maps in the public domain. The Catasto maps have been purchased from the Italian Archivio di Stato as jp2 files comprising 5.7GB for this precise purpose. The maps are already open access on the website of the Archivio di Stato under a CC-BY-NC-SA license and will not be published through the project.
2. Gazetteer database. The database will be maintained during the runtime of the project, and will be used by the team to digitize data from the land registers belonging to the maps (brogliardi), which have been purchased. Additional toponyms and names of historic property owners will be derived from other maps and publications. After the project is complete, the data will be integrated with the GIS system, and archived in standard formats (CSV attribute tables and GeoJSON, compliant to the Linked Places profile).
3. Image server. To facilitate digitization work on the gazetteer database, an open source IIIF image server (Cantaloupe) will be set up to host map and land register scans. We expect a volume of approx. 5,000 images total and have an estimated 500GB storage requirement maximum. This system will be maintained during the runtime of the project.
4. New data added to the already existing epigraphic database [EDR](#). In particular, about 8,000 new records currently on paper files at La Sapienza University and collected over decades as well as published inscriptions from the Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum and other publications not yet included in the database

¹ Several datasets may be included into a single DMP.

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will be added, to the existing database counting about 26,000 records.

5. PostgreSQL database based on published and unpublished archaeological and archival materials and their interpretation. The exact size is currently difficult to assess but will be rather limited due to the fact that it will mostly be text records. This will be a working database only that facilitates research but is not intended for publication.
6. Bibliography of secondary literature assembled and shared through the open-source programme [Zotero](#) – c. 3MB

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1. MAKING DATA FINDABLE *(dataset description: metadata, persistent and unique identifiers e.g., DOI)*

1.-3. The vectorized mapsheets and gazetteer database will be part of the GIS system and be stored for a minimum of 5 yrs after the end of the project on the project website. It is also hoped that it will be included in the GIS system [SITAR](#) of the Soprintendenza Speciale di Roma, and open access platform that also contains archaeological and geographical data of different origin. In addition, static snapshots of the data will be archived in standard formats (CSV attribute tables, GeoJSON spatial data). Geo-data produced from digitizing the map sheets of the Catasto Gregoriano will be integrated into the GIS system, and additionally be archived as downloadable files. This concerns: i) geo-referenced images (GeoTIFF format); ii) geo-referenced vector data for cadastral boundaries, produced manually as machine learning ground truth; iii) geo-referenced vector data for cadastral boundaries extracted automatically (GeoJSON format). Code and all data mentioned above will be deposited and versioned in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>).

4. The EDR database is an existing open-access online databases of the epigraphy of Rome maintained by the Sapienza University (scientific responsible Silvia Orlandi) and indexed by Europeana. It is the most authoritative epigraphic database worldwide and an established resource within the field. The EDR database claims a F2 level according to the FAIR principles.

5. This dataset will not be published as it will contain very preliminary information and a lot of data that are protected by the copyright of other parties (e.g. archives, publications under copyright, museums). Each record will be assigned a unique identifier and will be stored in a fully searchable resource (i.e. PostgreSQL database). The database will be compliant to the F4 level of the FAIR principles

6. The bibliography will be published as data sets in the free and open-source reference management programme Zotero. It will be accessible through the project website for at least 5 yrs after the end of the funding period and deposited also in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>).

A project website will be created and will receive a URL from the Scuola Normale Superiore. The website will contain a description of the project, staff involved, news and activities as well as links to any resources and publications resulting from the research. It will remain accessible through the SNS website for at least five years after the end of the project and findable through keywords.

2. MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE *(which data will be made openly available and if some datasets remain closed, the reasons for not giving access; where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited (repository?); how the data can be accessed (are relevant software tools/methods provided?)*

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- 1.-2. For the GIS system, see under 1.1-3 above. Zendo is accessible to humans via web and machines via a REST API. Zenodo supports harvesting via the OAI-PMH.
3. The image server will not be made available as a public resource. It will be infrastructure to support the digitization process for the project team.
4. The EDR database is an open access resource claiming A1 level of accessibility of the FAIR principles. Data and metadata are accessible by humans by web forms and pages and by machines by a REST API.
5. This dataset will not be made publicly available. It will be a working tool with all its imperfections. It will also contain a lot of data that are protected by the copy right of other parties (e.g. archives, publications under copyright, museums).
6. The bibliography will be published as data sets in the open-source, free-ware reference management programme Zotero. It will be accessible through the project website hosted by the Scuola Normale Superiore for at least 5 yrs after the end of the funding period. It will also be deposited in Zenodo.

3. MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE *(which standard or field-specific data and metadata vocabularies and methods will be used)*

- 1.-2. Spatial data will be stored in standard, open formats. The digitized map sheets from the Catasto Greogriano are originally in high-resolution (at least 10.000 x 10.000 pixels), in JPEG 2000 format. Geo-referenced versions of the map sheets will be stored in GeoTIFF format. Ground control points, which are produced manually in order to geo-reference the map sheets, are created using the open source AllMaps Editor. During the project, they are regularly backed up and stored in JSON format. Vector data of cadastral boundaries depicted in the map sheets is produced in two modes: once by tracing them manually, to serve as training and verification data for later automated methods; and once as a result of the automated tracing. Manual annotation is performed in the cloud-based Recogito annotation platform, which complies to the open W3C Web Annotation standard, and backed up regularly to a project server at AIT. Automated results are stored in a similar (possibly JSON or XML-based format such as SVG -yet to be defined) and backed up at AIT. Geo-referenced copies of the cadastral boundary shapes will be stored as GeoJSON polygon and polyline features (geo-referenced shapes in WGS84 lat/lon coordinates). The data and code released through Zenodo will follow the DataCite metadata schema.
4. EDR claims a I1 level of the FAIR Principles since its data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.

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5. This dataset, even if not public, will integrate identifiers from other external databases (qualified references to other data) and will use, when possible, shared and fully documented vocabularies. Its content will be available not only via web forms but also as a RESTfull API and a GraphQL API. It will be compliant to I3 level of the FAIR principles.

6. The bibliography will be accessible through the project website be deposited in Zenodo.

The web site is a data presentation portal, not properly designed to be machine readable (the item 4 database, instead, will be machine readable), but it will inherit from the database most of the interoperable features: such as shared references and documented vocabularies.

Zotero implements a fully interoperable and well documented platform, used by a wide and diverse community of users. It implements DataCite metadata schema to increase interoperability.

4. INCREASE DATA RE-USE (*what data will remain re-usable and for how long, is embargo foreseen; how the data is licensed; data quality assurance procedures*)

1.-2. i) all data produced will be exported and archived outside of the database as well, in standard, text-based formats, specifically CSV and GeoJSON. ii) DB maintenance itself will be guaranteed by SNS for a period of 10 years. iii) all software employed will be open source software, in particular the Open Source DB management system Directus (<https://directus.io/>), and the Cantaloupe IIIF image server (<https://cantaloupe-project.github.io/>). All data integrated in the GIS system will remain reusable for at least 5 yrs after the end of the project through the SNS website, but permanently in Zenodo and likely in SITAR if it integrates it in their platform. This has preliminarily been agreed with the Soprintendenza Speciale Archeologia Belle Arti e Paesaggio di Roma. We will apply for a CC BY SA license for the Catasto-based GIS system. The programmes through which it is being provided are all open-source. No embargo is foreseen after the end of the funding period, and we aim to make the data accessible even before then as soon as we are satisfied with the quality. Newly developed methodology will also be published in data and methods papers where the results merit such publication.

3. The image server will not be made available as a public resource; it is a temporary working instrument only.

4. The existence and maintenance of the EDR database is secured for the long term through an institutional collaboration of the project with the DigiLab interdepartmental research center of Sapienza, providing IT infrastructure and development resources to the database. All data relative to inscriptions are

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released with CC BY-SA 4.0 license. Data added to EDR will immediately be available open access.

5. The data of the working database will not be available to the general public and only be re-used by members of the project team, if at all.

6. The bibliography will be available on the project website for at least 5 years after the end of the funding period and deposited in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>). We are contemplating its publication and regular updating already during the funding period but it will be available by the end of the project at the very latest.

5. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES and DATA SECURITY *(estimated costs for making the project data open access and potential value of long-term data preservation; procedures for data backup and recovery; transfer of sensitive data and secure storage in repositories for long term preservation and curation)*

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1. Any costs for storing and making the GIS data open access for up to 5 yrs after the end of the funding period will be carried by the Scuola Normale Superiore. It is intended to preserve and maintain the data for at least another 5 years, and hopefully indefinitely through the [GARR Consortium](#). The required fees have been included in the project budget.
2. The EDR database is being hosted and maintained by La Sapienza University indefinitely with no costs for the project.
3. Any costs for storing and making the website data (incl. the bibliography) open access for up to 5 yrs after the end of the funding period will be carried by the Scuola Normale Superiore.

There are no sensitive data that need to be stored.

DISCLAIMER. Please note that the ERC Data Management Plan is not a part of the Ethics Review. It is the responsibility of the Principal Investigator to inform the ERCEA Ethics Team of any ethics issues/concerns regarding the collection, processing, sharing and storage of data in relation to the project.